

D7.2: BEACON promotional activities and engagement report (1)

WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion

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List of Acronyms

Acronyms	Explanation
AB	Advisory Board
AgI	Agricultural Insurance
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
EO	Earth Observation
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package

2. Dissemination and communication tools

During the previous period -16months from the beginning of the project-, all BEACON communication tools, and promotional material were developed. Namely the BEACON logo, several templates, a project fiche and the project brochure, the project website and the social media accounts. Moreover, both the first three BEACON newsletters were issued and the first mapping of relevant projects took place. In addition, the project's "Lighthouse Customers" group was established and is constantly being populated counting at the moment 16 members from Europe and beyond. The communication team elaborated the "BEACON KPIs' detailed action plan" as an ad hoc internal working document that essentially breaks down a time specific set of necessary activities to satisfy all KPIs by the end of the project.

2.1 The BEACON Website

The BEACON website – one pager available at <http://info.beacon-h2020.com/>, was developed and released on the 25th of April 2019 (M4). The official BEACON website <https://beacon-h2020.com/> has been running since the 24th of June (M6) and contains basic information about the project (about), also introducing the main objectives (concept) and services of BEACON. Relevant partners information is also included and an intranet section with limited access to partners only has been developed for intra-consortium communications, also serving a depository of online documents and forms, as well as dissemination reports.

A dedicated section containing information and links to project deliverables (only public deliverables), and a depository of project's promotional material has also been included. A news section covers recent news items, published newsletters (including links to download current and archived newsletters) and other relevant project publications.

Additionally, a dedicated business blog section on the website, the BEACON Content hub, is hosting articles and posts covering different aspects relating to AgI. The Content hub acts as a focal point for the deployment of the Content and Growth Hacking strategy, developed under WP6 aiming to communicate customized content articles to AgI target audiences (SMEs), enhance their active engagement in BEACON and optimally attract upcoming BEACON customers.

The BEACON webpage is already available in English, Spanish, German and Serbian and is soon to be live in Greek too. Multiple languages – mainly the languages spoken from project partners – will help in the diffusion of information and reach to the general public and project stakeholders.

The Privacy Policy, together with the Terms and Conditions have also been included in the BEACON website, that is a set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

Figure 1: The BEACON project website

Webpage visits

Webpage visits as well as the general performance of the BEACON webpage are tracked using Google Analytics.

Figure 2: BEACON website views and growth

The BEACON webpage traffic is progressively increasing at a median rate of 28% (page views). Average monthly web traffic growth is expected to decrease and stabilize in the following months. A webpage opening attracts a high volume of traffic and visits. Maintaining and growing that volume afterwards is the challenge ahead. Constant feeding the webpage with news, articles, new languages and other features is expected to maintain its growth rate.

Additionally, and in order to better measure traffic quality, unique pageviews to the webpage is also being tracked and is analysed later in the relative chapter (Chapter 4).

2.2 The BEACON Social Media

BEACON has achieved a strong presence in social media, enhancing its reach-out to target audiences and broad public and has managed to succeed in an active interaction with them. Focus has been given to those social media that partners have been already using effectively into their day-to-day communications but are also of general public acceptance.

BEACON project has established (M4) a social media account for Twitter, a dedicated Facebook page, a project dedicated group on LinkedIn, as well as a You Tube channel.

Some hashtags, which are being used for the BEACON project, are the following: #BEACON; #insurance; #blockchain; #agtech; #eo; #agri; #AgI_Innovation; #remotesensing; #innovativesolutions; #agribusiness; #h2020; #eu.

Facebook page

<https://www.facebook.com/beaconh2020/>

BEACON's Facebook page was created on the 22/4/2019. It focuses at establishing direct communications with target audiences, both in terms of relevant groups (e.g. Agricultural Insurance Brokers) as well as individuals, and other audiences' segments. Although Facebook is considered as a main channel for communications of individuals, the BEACON Facebook page serves for broader communications, as well as B2C ones.

Figure 3: BEACON's Facebook page

Figure 5: BEACON Facebook account followers and growth

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Twitter account

https://twitter.com/BEACON_Agl

The BEACON twitter account is being used for amplifying communications to a large community of active stakeholders, as well as for propagation of news and project developments. Regular Twitter chats focus at attracting and engaging with target audiences leading also to the establishment of a trusted BEACON network, enlarging the outreach to broad and targeted audiences.

Figure 6: BEACON Twitter account

To date (3-4-2020), the BEACON twitter account has 145 followers. The followers base may be categorized in four main groups, specifically private companies, research – academia, relative research projects and individuals of relative to the project activities. It needs to be noted that BEACON has achieved networking with a number of Horizon 2020 Projects through its Twitter account and they are namely:

- | | | |
|-----------|------------|------------|
| EFFECT | ATLAS | agROBOfood |
| CANDELA | OPTIMA | Salsa |
| Stargate | DEEP | SIEUSOIL |
| PoliRural | Swinostics | Ecobreed |
| TRUSTS | DIONE | ROSIN |
| SURE-Farm | STARTUP3 | LandSense |
| Pledger | e-shape | Block.IS |

Content strategy focuses on related trending topics such as: Agricultural Insurance Market, Climate Change, Blockchain and Agricultural Technology. BEACON has in total 105 tweets (3/4/2020). Project partners Twitter accounts are also mentioned when appropriate, whilst project partners also actively mention @BEACON_Agl in their tweets and use common hashtags.

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Figure 7: BEACON Tweets example

BEACON Twitter account is growing stably and after the rapid growth that follows the opening of an account, growth is at a median monthly rate of 19%.

Figure 8: BEACON Twitter account followers & growth

LinkedIn Group

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13699653/>

The BEACON dedicated LinkedIn group is being extensively used for networking purposes, enabling the promotion of BEACON amongst a broad community of professionals within AgI as well as other segments of BEACON's target audiences. Furthermore, BEACON LinkedIn account has achieved interaction with representatives of other relevant groups such as: Agricultural Insurance; Agribusiness and Farm Insurance Specialist (AFIS), Agricultural Insurance – Academic group etc., enhancing its outreach and engagement with other target audiences.

Figure 9: BEACON LinkedIn account

To this date (3-4-2020), the LinkedIn account counts 289 members. Median growth rate is at 3% but as it can be seen from the next graph growth is not stable showing intense peaks during specific periods. This has been identified and corrective actions took place managing to even out growth over the last three months. Growth is expected to stabilise in the following semester. New posts on events, informative videos, news and polls have increased reach to new members. Overall, 112 posts have been published on the LinkedIn account.

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Figure 10: BEACON LinkedIn followers & growth

YouTube Channel

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YkH130SVs0s>

YouTube is currently the second most popular website in the world. Even though most people don't think of YouTube primarily as a search engine, that's exactly what most visitors do on the site. YouTube's not just the second most popular website; it's also the second most popular search engine – topped only by Google. This means that the platform presents a huge potential for reach for to stakeholders. To this end BEACON has created a YouTube channel to increase the reach of project videos produced.

The BEACON channel was created on the 2nd of October 2019 and up to now, 6 BEACON videos produced and 2 more of relevant content have been published. These videos have been viewed 404 times so far (April 7).

Figure 11: BEACON YouTube Channel videos

YouTube analytics provide valuable information regarding how viewers came to find BEACON content (traffic source -figure 12). 52% of traffic was achieved through the BEACON website, 22.3% came from external sources (traffic source: external -figure 13), whilst YouTube search and Suggested videos have added to the stakeholder reach by a 10.1% (7.4% and 2.7% respectively).

Figure 12: You Tube Traffic source typed

Figure 13: You Tube Traffic source: external

Social media videos

Five videos have been produced and uploaded on the project’s social media accounts, additional to the ones that have been uploaded on the You Tube channel.

Figure 14: Social media videos

BEACON podcast

In order to enrich the audiovisual communication channels, the first episode of a series of podcasts, was produced (23rd Jan 2020) and communicated through the project’s website and social media.

Figure 15: BEACON podcast

2.3 BEACON promotional material

The BEACON project has produced a series of promotional materials to enhance the promotion of the BEACON tools and services. Promotional materials are being used at project related and other events that BEACON partners will be present, as well as in meetings and other project promotional activities.

These include:

- A brochure and a set of different factsheets
- A short project fiche - BEACON one pager
- Presentation template
- Deliverable templates
- Press release template
- A Roll-up and poster

Figure 16. BEACON one pager

Figure 17: BEACON press release

Figure 18: BEACON deliverables template (cover page)

Figure 19: BEACON roll-up

Figure 20: BEACON Brochure

The Tool

UNDERWRITING
Confidently empower your underwriting with access to the latest historical data and (localized) weather forecast data.

CONTRACT MONITORING
Powered by remote sensing imagery, BEACON allows for efficient, seamless smart contract monitoring your clients deserve - remotely and in real time.

DAMAGE ASSESSMENT
Tailored satellite-based information services so you get a more accurate damage assessment, claims adjustment & fraud detection.

SMART CONTRACTS
Powered by Blockchain technology, BEACON brings the Smart Contracts, enabling automatically pay out damages to insured parties.

Redefining Agriculture Insurance tools
The ultimate solution for growing agri-insurance businesses

BEACON

Project Partners

Your Challenges

- Understand future Weather uncertainty
- Planning Agri activities
- Establish long-term competitive advantage
- Designing new Agri-Insurance Products

Your Gains

- Evaluate Risk**
 - Continuously monitor weather risks. Parcels data
 - Alert Agri of high-risk future events
 - Assess risk based on long-term DECADAL forecasting
- Increase Efficiency**
 - Personalise underwriting
 - Improve claims processing
 - Enable targeted on spot visits
 - Efficient operational planning / staffing
 - Evaluate faster, save time
- Reduce Costs**
 - Ensure only valid claims are paid
 - Prevent fraud by verifying contracts
 - Prevent property damage and reduction of crop loss through timely alerts
 - Reduce O&A costs
- Increase Customer Loyalty**
 - Create dynamic pricing based on actual risk
 - Swiftly verify claims with acceptable results.
 - Enable a transparent framework positively perceived by the insured

BEACON Services

BEACON services enable the Agri sector to alleviate the effect of weather uncertainty when estimating risk of Agri products, reduce the number of on-site visits for claim verification, reduce operational and administrative costs for monitoring of insured indexes and contract handling, and design more accurate and personalized contracts.

Crop Monitoring

Damage Progress Early Warning

Damage Assessment Calculator

Weather Risk Probability

Anti-Fraud Inspector

Figure 21: BEACON poster

Figure 22: BEACON presentation template (slide 1)

3. Engagement actions and results

Ensuring a dynamic interaction with the BEACON targeted audiences is of utmost importance so as to ensure a long-term impact and market-uptake of the project outcomes, with the BEACON consortium composition, allowing access to all the categories of audiences. Direct and indirect access through the partners networks, ensure that the dissemination activities will be effective and successfully achieve high reach and impact KPI's.

The main target audience, AgI companies (already involved in the project as well as additional ones) will be invited to participate and be actively engaged in the project through the “Lighthouse customers” group, being the first users of BEACON and further connect the project to the AgI sector. Their active engagement and interaction within the project aim at generating positive perceptions derived by the recognition of BEACON's economic, social, and operational benefits. This will not only work as an amplifier in the dissemination of the project outcomes but also will optimally enable the creation of BEACON's pool of potential future customers.

Engagement with other stakeholders potentially benefiting by the BEACON toolbox, services and outcomes (in and out of the AgI sector), will also be established mainly focusing on raising awareness and diffusing project advancements and results, creating interest and opportunities for further exploitation routes of BEACON's solutions and outcomes.

In overall, active engagement will support and set the base for the development of the co-creation approach. Reaching out to target audiences and feeding necessary information will prepare the ground for the full iteration cycles that will follow.

Engagement actions that have been taken up so far are presented in the following.

3.1 BEACON Newsletters

BEACON e-Newsletters are composed and published in the project website and social media, but are also distributed to the consortium members, Lighthouse customers, the “AgI Enablers” as well as networks and direct contacts within the BEACON ecosystem of stakeholders. The newsletters serve as a tool to communicate key updates and developments to the BEACON ecosystem of stakeholders and are aiming to keep them informed and engaged.

The BEACON newsletter is published regularly. The first three newsletters are available on <https://beacon-h2020.com/news-media/> and the aim is to publish totally a number of 10 newsletters.

Figure 23: Examples of BEACON Newsletters

A specific newsletter recipients list has already been created and is constantly being populated by a specific option for subscription to the list of newsletter recipients, that has been included in two parts of the BEACON website. The figure that follows depicts the number of registered stakeholders – newsletter recipients and the networks growth over the project’s lifetime. Registration of stakeholders is stabilizing over time and the median growth value is 8%.

Figure 24: BEACON Newsletter subscribers and growth

Moreover, with the aim to enlarge the pool of the newsletter subscribers, an exclusive repetitive campaign, using tailored made cards, is running through the project’s social media in order to increase their number.

Figure 25: BEACON Newsletter subscription card

Figure 27: BEACON Twitter account Retweets and Likes

YouTube channel

BEACON videos on the YouTube channel have engaged stakeholders for a total of 4.12 hours. In the following figure total watch time per video is presented. Highest engagement has been achieved by the BEACON EU Project video where the project is being presented (1.87h) but it needs to be noted that it is the first video released.

Figure 28: BEACON videos engagement ranking

Facebook page

Engagement in Facebook is provided by its analytics where the main metrics monitored regard:

- **Actions on Page:** shows the number of actions people have taken on the page (i.e. who clicked on it)

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Figure 30: Facebook posts engagement rate

 LinkedIn group

LinkedIn does not provide analytics for Group accounts. User engagement can nonetheless be derived by Post Likes. LinkedIn account has collected 861 likes for 112 posts (3/4/2020) which averages at about 8 likes per post, whilst the mean growth rate of reactions is at 16% showing thus a satisfactory user engagement.

Figure 31: LinkedIn user engagement and growth

Through LinkedIn account an encouraging comment was collected (4/9/2019) from a member based in Romania expressing an interest on BEACON services. Specifically, he mentioned “It would be interesting to have a company presence in Romania!”

Figure 32: Example of LinkedIn user engagement / interaction

3.3 BEACON Polls

In order to ensure the stakeholders' engagement ETAM has organized polls through the social media (redirecting to the website) to encourage social media "friends" to express their opinion on questions relevant to the project.

Specifically, two BEACON polls have been organised asking stakeholders to provide feedback on the following:

BEACON poll#1

Stakeholders were asked to rate the importance of challenges Agricultural Insurance faces so as to receive feedback on how user of services perceive their gravity.

As a means of engagement, the first BEACON poll, was released in 5 languages (English, French, Italian, Spanish and Greek) and its results were heavily communicated. The outcome was a statistically significant set of answers that among other highlighted the correct design of the project. This poll managed to collect 72 answers.

Figure 33: BEACON poll#1 card

 BEACON poll#2

The second poll that is still running is asking stakeholders which of the BEACON services they consider to be of greater importance in order to engage them in the project but at the same time provoke interest at the services under development.

Figure 34: BEACON poll#2 card

3.4 Agricultural Insurance Enablers

The **Agricultural Insurance (AgI) Enablers** BEACON Advisory Board (AB), has been established and it is a counselling body consisting of external experts, aiming to provide advice and guidance for the development of the project and ensure high quality and excellence in achieving the project results. It

consists of 6 members, Dr. ATHANASIADIS Ioannis, Mrs. VAKAKI Eleni, Mr. GENILLARD Christopher, Mr. MEEUSEN Paul, Dr. ATZBERGER Clement and Ms. PANKAJ Shilpa. The members were selected on the basis of their expertise and experience in relevant to the BEACON aspects and potential contributions to the realization of current project activities.

The AgI Enablers have actively been engaged in the project, by taking part in – individual members – meetings and providing feedback (experts' recommendations, partners' comments, important issues raised, etc.).

3.5 Lighthouse Customers

The BEACON Lighthouse Customers is a group of well-established Agricultural Insurance providers that will be involved in the co-development and co-validation process of the BEACON toolbox, ensuring that the resulting tool will match the Agricultural Insurance sector workflow as well as current and future needs.

Following a series of conducted face-to-face and Skype meetings with Agricultural Insurance providers the list of confirmed BEACON Lighthouse Customers is provided below.

1. Agrisk - crop insurance broker (HUNGARY)
2. Agrupación Española de Entidades Aseguradoras de los Seguros Agrarios Combinados S.A. (SPAIN)
3. AON (UK)
4. ASUA (UK)
5. Az Sigorta (AZERBAIJAN)
6. B3i (SWITZERLAND)
7. DDOR NOVI SAD Osiguranje (SERBIA)
8. Financial and Insurance Services – Socodevi (CANADA)
9. Generali Osiguranje (SERBIA)
10. Halk Osiguruvanje A.D. (SKOPJE, NORTH MACEDONIA)
11. HDFC ERGO General Insurance Company (INDIA)
12. Hellenic Agricultural Insurance Organisation – ELGA (GREECE)
13. Interamerican (GREECE)
14. Microinsurance Catastrophe Risk Organisation - MiCRO (BARBADOS)
15. Triglav Osiguranje (SERBIA)
16. WIENER Osiguranje VIG (BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA)

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Partner	Description of activity	Date and place of activity
FCE	EO data and cartography - potential for innovation - lecture and presentation at the Faculty of geodesy, University of Zagreb	22 October 2019, Zagreb, Croatia
FCE	Copernicus Hackathon Zagreb 23-24.10.2019.	23-24 October 2019, Zagreb

Telephone / e-mail engagements with a series of stakeholders have taken place. An important stakeholder that has been contacted is the Bank of Greece and specifically the Department of Private Insurance Supervision. Direct contact with the Manager of the Department Ms Ioanna Seliniotaki was achieved and an intention to cooperate and take part in project meetings was expressed.

Finally, BEACON has published a series of press releases, PR articles in reg-nat-EU press and in business journals and scientific articles (results presented in the KPI section). These publications attract significant number of stakeholders and mainly of the core group.

The BEACON partners' scientific articles that were published during the first year of the project are the following:

- A peer-reviewed paper titled "Redefining Agricultural Insurance services using Earth Observation data". The case of "Beacon project." was presented during the 13th ISESS (International Symposium on Environmental Software Systems) conference in Wageningen (NL), on 6 February 2020. The paper has also been selected to be published in Volume 554 of the IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology series as well as in the book, Environmental Software Systems. Data Science in Action, on behalf of Springer (a Springer Nature brand).
- Furthermore, another paper was published by BEACON in the Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences (EGU) titled "Evaluation of a combined drought indicator and its potential for agricultural drought prediction in southern Spain".

Figure 35: Examples of BEACON publications

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Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences EGU

Statistical analysis for satellite-index-based insurance to define damaged pasture thresholds

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Abstract. Vegetation indices based on satellite images, such as the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), have been used in countries like the USA, Canada and Spain for damaged pasture and forage insurance over the last few years. This type of agricultural insurance is – Differences between normal and GEV distributions are higher during spring and autumn, which are transition periods in the precipitation regimes. – NDVI damage threshold shows evident differences us

Redefining Agricultural Insurance services using Earth Observation data. The case of Beacon project.

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Abstract. BEACON is a market-led project that couples cutting edge Earth Observation (EO) technology with weather intelligence and blockchain to deliver a toolbox for the Agricultural Insurance (AgI) sector with timely cost-efficient and actionable insights for the agri-insurance industry. BEACON enables insurance companies to exploit the untapped market potential of AgI, while contributing to the redefinition of existing AgI products and services. The Damage Assessment Calculator of BEACON employs remote sensing techniques in order to improve the quality and cost-effectiveness of agri-insurance by: i) increasing the objectivity of the experts' field inspections; ii) reducing the cost of field visits and iii) increasing farmers' confidence in the estimation results, given the significant economic impact of insurance estimation. The paper provides an analysis of different types of EO data and remote sensing techniques implemented in the operational workflow of BEACON that can be used by AgI companies to provide safe and reliable results on storms, floods, wildfires and droughts damage on crops.

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Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences EGU

Evaluation of a combined drought indicator and its potential for agricultural drought prediction in southern Spain

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no-tillfarmer.com/articles/9550-beacon-boosts-agricultural-insurance

TOPICS ADVERTISE FOLLOW US f in y 0 ITEMS

Beacon Boosts Agricultural Insurance

March 18, 2020 | Posted in Precision Ag

The BEACON Horizon 2020 research project aspires to deliver a blockchain-fueled toolbox that couples cutting edge Earth Observation (EO) technology with weather intelligence to deliver cost-efficient and actionable insights for the agri-insurance industry.

BEACON started a year ago and currently all work-packages are in full operation. Over this first 12-month journey, BEACON started, evolved and is already making a difference with its mark in the Agricultural Insurance (AgI) sector. Over this period the project team worked on identifying AgI actors' requirements and needs and processing modules that will operationally produce the earth observation products and meteorological data, to drive the BEACON services.

BEACON
 Boosting Agricultural Insurance based on Earth Observation data

PRESS RELEASE

BEACON boosts Agricultural Insurance

The BEACON project (502) researches and develops a toolbox that combines Earth Observation (EO) technology with weather intelligence to deliver cost-efficient and actionable insights for the agri-insurance industry.

BEACON started a year ago and currently all work-packages are in full operation. Over this first 12-month journey, BEACON started, evolved and is already making a difference with its mark in the Agricultural Insurance (AgI) sector. Over this period the project team worked on identifying AgI actors' requirements and needs and processing modules that will operationally produce the earth observation products and meteorological data, to drive the BEACON services.

The BEACON toolbox includes:

- Cloud Monitoring
- Soil Moisture Monitoring
- Fire Risk Assessment
- Damage Assessment Calculator
- Agri-InsurTech Platform

The 1st operational BEACON toolbox is in full operation and the future steps of the pilot also align with insurance services and farmer field operations to be in place.

Aligned with BEACON partners, 13 European countries that are already on board the project, focusing on providing a cutting-edge solution for the Agricultural Insurance sector, experts' insights and customer feedback will be incorporated.

To find out more on how BEACON technology the Agricultural Insurance sector you can browse the webpage, subscribe to the newsletter. Make the most of our content and watch the next developments. Please don't miss our content in the Research of Interest and the BEACON Content Hub as well.

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News

BEACON boosts Agricultural Insurance

The 1st operational BEACON toolbox is available.

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4. Analysis of results

In order to achieve the successful implementation of Communication and Dissemination activities, and fulfillment of the relevant objectives, a systematic monitoring is being carried out throughout the project implementation. Regular monitoring allows the identification of possible risks and deviations from the DEC objectives and performance indicators, and the timely planning of any necessary corrections actions to address potential implementation problems.

An online form has been created for reporting all DEC activities partners perform. The form is available to all partners via the Intranet section of the BEACON project website, and all reported activity is being stored at the projects' documents repository (Dropbox file).

The table below presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) which are being used to evaluate the performance of the project's actions.

Table 3: Key Performance Indicators

Key Performance indicators	Target value	Achieved by M6		Achieved by M12		Achieved by M17	
Project website pageviews	60,000	N/A		5,564		9,089	
Social media followers	6,000	BEACON	BEACON and Partners	BEACON	BEACON and Partners	BEACON	BEACON and Partners
		LinkedIn: 182	LinkedIn: 587	LinkedIn: 264	LinkedIn: 196,076	LinkedIn: 289	LinkedIn: 197,377
		Facebook: 61	Facebook: 5,588	Facebook: 367	Facebook: 39,735	Facebook: 367	Facebook: 39,777
		Twitter: 22	Twitter: 986	Twitter: 99	Twitter: 46,121	Twitter: 440	Twitter: 47,646
		265	7,161	730	281,932	1,096	284,800
Sector-specific newsletters	10	1		2		3	
Newsletter subscribers	2,000	32		122		140	
Blog posts	100	0		17		23	
Videos released	30	1		4		9	
PR articles published in reg-nat-EU press	200	8		20		22	
Publications in business journals	5	2		5		5	
Distributed printed material	5,000	0		0		0	
Presentations in forums, workshops relevant to project results	10	7		8		9	

Key Performance indicators	Target value	Achieved by M6	Achieved by M12	Achieved by M17
Meetings (Agl; EO; Farmers Organisations; Institutions (EU/Internat.))	35	32	54	54
Informal person-to-person meetings with relevant national stakeholders	85	13	18	23

🌐 Online presence

The online strategy of the DEC Plan of BEACON is based on: its webpage, its social media accounts, blog publications, online media coverages of the project partners, as well as on the support that the online EU Communication routes (Cordis, EIP-Agri webpages) offer. In general, the strategy is consolidated, and it is helping achieve the targets and impact expected in the DEC Plan. Project partners offer active support to all online communication actions. Besides partners have well established online media audiences which is crucial for the ultimate success of the online communication of the project.

The target for the project website pageviews is 60,000 views. So far and over the 10 months the website has been operational it has had 9,089 views. This number of views represents 15.15% of the targeted views. It is expected that as the project progresses and over the next 20 months of the Beacon lifespan the target is difficult to be reached.

The target for social media followers is 6,000 and by now this target has been reached given the great number of the partners' social media followers (284,800).

Blog posts have reached twenty-three out of the one hundred targeted (23/100). Note that the dedicated section on the website has not been functional from the beginning of the website operation and that twenty posts have been achieved over the last five months. The content of the blog would benefit from posts that focus on processes of the project or specific issues related to project results and their implementation in the Agri sector.

Nine out the thirty BEACON videos have been released and are available on the project's You Tube channel and rest social media.

Figure 36: Example of EU BEACON publication

Publications / Papers

Three out of ten Sector-specific newsletters have been published and planning for newsletter publishing per semester is followed. The KPI for Publications in business journals has already been achieved (5/5). Twenty-two out of two hundred (22/200) press release articles have been published in reg-nat-EU press. These publications focus on presentations of the project and on the description of some of its processes. In the future, once results start to come out, publishing of new papers and technical publications will increase. Development of project materials has been completed as early as month 4 but it has been decided that printed material will be mainly distributed during the last phase (M 25-37) of the project when the focus will be at promoting concrete BEACON results.

An area that can be improved is the number of Newsletter subscribers. So far only 7.1% of the target has been reached (142/2000 subscribers) and it needs to be promoted by partners and their online activity, as GDPR rules and the need for subscription causes reluctancies to the stakeholders. This argument can be supported by the fact that a significant number of active of social media followers have not subscribed to the newsletter.

Event participation

Nine out of ten (9/10) presentations in forums, workshops relevant to project results have already been carried out by project partners. The KPI for Meetings (Agl; EO; Farmers Organisations; Institutions (EU/International) has been surpassed since month 12 (54/35) whilst twenty tree out of the targeted eighty five (23/85) informal person-to-person meetings with relevant national stakeholders have been carried out. BEACON project partners are very active and involve themselves in many communication actions and as it is apparent from the aforementioned results these KPIs will easily be reached.

As explained before, constant monitoring of project indicators can allow corrective actions to be timely taken, in case any of the indicators is not achieving the expected growth.

5. Next steps

According to the DEC Plan during this first reporting period the goal was to “Reach out and Raise awareness”. This phase has an approach-oriented content, for the establishment of the ecosystem of stakeholders, aiming to ensure wide project presentation on objectives, expected results and promote pilots’ activities. Raising awareness is a continuous activity that will be deployed all along the project lifespan.

With the aim of increasing the awareness of major stakeholders, several Think tanks, COPA members and ENRD contact points were listed in order to plan relevant communication, dissemination and engagement activities in the next steps of this phase. Along with the deployment of pilot cases, further promotional activities will focus at triggering the interest of target audiences and also mobilize the Lighthouse customers to actively connect with the BEACON toolbox and get engaged in relevant project activities.

During the second phase (M18 – 25) the aim is to create a more targeted awareness regarding BEACON. The goal is to Attract - Engage – Interact. Advancements and techniques implemented for overcoming known challenges in the AgI sector and their added value towards specific stakeholders and communities within the BEACON ecosystem, will be transposed into storytelling and key messages to attract active engagement of end users.

The last phase (M 25-37) will focus at promoting concrete BEACON results to its key stakeholders, aiming at the creation of BEACON customer base, establishing a positive word of mouth and building upon pilot success stories and Lighthouse customers feedback. All activities during the 3rd phase will focus on attracting and delivering more users-actors to the BEACON toolbox, to establish mutual beneficial synergies with AgI actors and strengthen further commercial links with them.

Short term planning and specifically for the next six (6) months the following actions have been scheduled

- a) Reinforce visual content and content from inside the project
- b) Increase page views and newsletter subscribers
- c) Content hub reinforcement
- d) Polls and recall surveys
- e) e-mail campaign for enhancing engagement
- f) Increase regularity of press releases and newsletters
- g) Videos and podcast productions
- h) Content development in native language
- i) Science web editors and journalists
- j) Further engagement of the Advisory Board as multipliers of communication
- k) Maintain regularity in posting and emphasis on images
- l) Connect with more H2020 projects
- m) Agri-consultants, Farmers’ collective bodies, Rural networks
- n) Social media development and balanced performance
- o) KPIs’ monitoring, further partners’ engagement and personalised recommendations

